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Research Article

Development and Assessment of Herbal Anti-Aging Cream Using Okra Mucilage and Rice Extracts

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ABSTRACT

Background: Skin aging is a complex process that destroys human skin when exposed to ultraviolet (UV) irradiation on a continuous basis. Skin wrinkling eventually results from a lack of collagen caused by reactive oxygen species produced by UV light exposure. Numerous phenolics and flavonoids found in basil have antioxidant qualities. This study aimed to create and evaluate an anti-aging face cream using rice extract, okra mucilage acetone extract, and okra mucilage extract extracts. **Method:** Various formulations of oil-in-water in water (O/W) anti-aging creams, designated as F1 to F6, were prepared with different concentrations of okra mucilage extract, acetone extract of okra mucilage, rice extract, and linseed oil. Each formulation underwent a comprehensive evaluation for pH level, viscosity, Spreadability, sensory attributes, homogeneity, appearance, and stability. To ensure safety even more, irritancy tests were performed. The formulations F1, F2, and F6 demonstrated advantageous characteristics such as Spreadability, homogeneity, uniformity, aesthetic appeal, and pH balance. Furthermore, they exhibited ease of removal without evidence of phase separation. Irritancy studies confirmed that no one of the formulations caused redness, swelling, inflammation, or irritation, indicating their suitability for skin application. **Results:** The main purpose behind this investigation was to develop a stable and functionally effective cream and to evaluate for good product performance of the prepared cream. The pH of the cream was found to be in the range of 6.3 to 6.9 which is good for skin pH. All the formulations of cream were shown pH nearer to skin required i.e. All the formulations of cream were shown pH nearer to skin required i.e pH of F1-6.31, F2-6.22, F3-6.43, F4-6.66, F5-6.57, and F6-6.70. The dye test confirms that all formulations were o/w type emulsion cream. But formulation (F1, F2 & F6) shows more stability in o/w type emulsion.

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All formulations produce a uniform distribution of extracts in cream. The formulations applied to the skin was easily removed by washing with tap water. All formulation shows no redness, edema, inflammation or irritation during irritancy studies. These formulations are safe to use for the skin. Accelerated stability testing of prepared formulations was conducted for all formulations at 40°C 1°C for 20 days. The formulations were kept both at room and elevated temperature and observed 20th day for the various parameters. Conclusion: Both the okra and rice extract formulations showed potent antioxidant activities and tyrosinase inhibition. The findings from these studies indicate that the formulation comprising okra and rice extracts, specifically F1, F2, and F6, exhibit higher levels of stability and safety compared to the other formulations. Conversely, the remaining formulations demonstrated instability and exhibited changes in color upon prolonged storage. As we know that it is not possible to increase the extent of efficiency of medicinal and cosmetic property of single plant extract, but by combining the different natural components can be possible to increase the efficacy of extracts. The results demonstrated that the formulated antiaging creams are safe and usable for the skin and having good potential for cosmetic product development.

INTRODUCTION

Skin aging is a continuous process resulting from the deterioration of cellular DNA and proteins. It's a widespread and predictable occurrence characterized by physiological changes in skin function. During aging, keratinocytes lose their ability to form a functional stratum corneum, and the production of neutral lipids slows down, leading to dry, wrinkled skin [1]. Herbs and plants have been valued for their utility in complementary medicine. Using cosmetics not only enhances external appearance but also promotes long-term health by addressing skin disorders. Whether synthetic or natural, ingredients in skin care formulations support skin health, texture, and integrity, providing moisture, preserving elasticity by reducing type I collagen degradation, and offering photoprotection [2]. Cosmetics also help manage skin properties over time by mitigating the production of free radicals in the skin. Cosmetic products act as a protective

barrier against harmful external and internal agents while enhancing skin beauty and attractiveness [3]. They play a crucial role in addressing various skin issues such as hyperpigmentation, wrinkles, and rough texture. The demand for herbal cosmetics is rapidly growing, underscoring their effectiveness and popularity in skincare [4,5].

Fig No. 1. Okra [6]

Okra, scientifically known as *Abelmoschus esculentus*, is a widely consumed vegetable in various international cuisines as shown in Fig No. 1. Currently, scientists are exploring the potential advantages of okra in promoting youthful skin and combating aging. Okra is rich in bioactive components, including vitamins, minerals, antioxidants, and polysaccharides, which have demonstrated anti-aging effects. The application of okra extracts directly onto the skin has been found to improve skin elasticity, diminish the appearance of wrinkles, and boost skin hydration. [7]. In recent years, there has been a growing quest for novel bioactive compounds aimed at preventing skin aging. Simultaneously, there's a rising interest in utilizing natural ingredients, preferably sourced from organic farming, in cosmetic formulations. Rice water emerges as a natural, cost-effective, and straightforward component that holds potential for incorporation into skincare items as shown in Fig No. 2. It can be derived from various rice varieties commonly consumed by humans and from by-products

generated by the rice industry, thus offering a means to elevate its value as a skincare ingredient [8].

Fig No. 2. Rice

Extraction of okra mucilage from okra pod

Okra pods can be found at nearby markets. Slice the pods thinly along their length, remove the seeds, and soak the slices in filtered water for 24 hours. To create an aqueous extract, press the soaked slices through muslin bags to extract the liquid. To isolate the mucilage, dilute the aqueous extract with an equal amount of alcohol. Rinse the mucilage with three times its volume of acetone. Filter out the acetone and separate the mucilage. Reserve a portion of the mucilage for sun drying as shown in Fig No. 3 [9] and Fig No. 4 and 5 shows the acetone extract of okra and okra mucilage.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Fig No.3. Extraction Process of Okra

Fig No. 4. Acetone extract of okra mucilage

Fig No. 5. Okra Mucilage

Extraction of Rice

Rice water prepared by the boiling method (RWB) involved boiling 400 grams of whole paddy rice grains in 1 liter of deionized water for 30 minutes. The resulting rice water was filtered using cotton gauze and then frozen at -30°C until needed as shown in Fig No. 6 [10].

Fig No. 6. Rice extract

Method of preparation of Okra Antiaging cream

The formula is shown in Table No. 1.

- Add the required amount of cetyl alcohol and EDTA in a sufficient quantity of water and

prepare a solution by heating on a hot plate at 40°C . [Solution 1]

- Take a required quantity of xantham gum and methylparaben in a sufficient quantity of water and prepare a solution by heating it on a hot plate at the same temperature. [Solution 2]
- Add solution 2 dropwise into solution 1 until both solutions get mixed properly and prepare a solution. [Solution 3]
- Add the required quantity of okra mucilage, acetone extract of okra mucilage, rice extract, beeswax, linseed oil, and arachis oil and mix properly, and prepare a solution by heating on a hot plate at the same temperature. [Solution 4]
- Add solution 3 dropwise into solution 4. When both phases got mixed properly, the formulated anti-aging cream was kept aside for about an hour in a cool and dry place in indirect sunlight until it was set completely and was used 48 hours after keeping at room temperature for stability and another analytical testing as shown in Fig No. 7, 8.

Table No. 1. Formulation Table

S no.	Ingredients	Role	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	Con.
1.	Okra mucilage [Pure drug]	API	10	—	20	—	30	—	% w/v
2.	Okra mucilage extract wh acetone	API	—	10	—	20	—	30	% w/v
3.	Rice extract	API	2.5	2.5	5	5	7.5	7.5	% w/v
4.	Cetyl alcohol	Humectant	5	5	5	5	5	5	% w/w
5.	Xantham gum	Thickening agent	5	5	5	5	5	5	% w/w
6.	EDTA	Chelating agent	2	2	2	2	2	2	% w/w
7.	Beeswax	Base	2	2	2	2	2	2	% w/w
8.	Ascorbic acid	Vitamin C	3	3	3	3	3	3	% w/w
9.	Linseed oil	Base	10	10	10	10	10	10	% w/v
10.	Methyl Paraben	Preservative	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	% w/w
11.	Arachis oil	Base	10	10	10	10	10	10	% w/v
12.	Purified Water (QS)	Vehicle	QS						

Fig No. 7. Formulations F1, F3, and F5 contain okra mucilage [pure form] and rice extract

Fig No. 8. Formulations F2, F4, and F6 contain acetone extract of okra mucilage and rice extract

Evaluation Parameters

The assessment of the okra antiaging cream involved the following criteria:

1. **Organoleptic properties:** The cream's appearance, including color, odor, and texture, was evaluated and graded based on these attributes Table No..2 presents the results.
2. **Type of Emulsion Determination (Dye Method):** A bright red dye was introduced into the cream, and a drop of the mixture was examined under a microscope on a slide. The cream was classified as water-in-oil (w/o) if the dispersed globules appeared red with a colorless continuous phase, and as oil-in-water (o/w) if the dispersed globules were colorless with a reddish continuous phase. Table No..3 displays the outcomes.
3. **pH of the cream:** The pH meter was calibrated using a standard buffer solution. The pH of the cream was measured after diluting 0.5 g of cream in 50 ml of distilled water. The findings are detailed in Table No..4.
4. **Homogeneity:** The consistency of the formulation was assessed visually and by touch to ensure even distribution.
5. **Visual Appearance:** The cream's overall look, including its color, pearlescence, and texture, was evaluated.
6. **After feel:** Emollience, slipperiness and the residual amount left on the skin after applying a fixed amount of cream were examined.
7. **Type of Smear:** The type of film or residue left on the skin post application was observed.

8. **Washability:** The ease of removing the applied cream was tested by rinsing the treated area with tap water. Results are documented in Table No.. 5.

9. **Irritancy Test:** A designated 1 square centimeter area on the left dorsal skin of human participants was marked. The cream was applied to this area, and any irritation, redness, or swelling was assessed at regular intervals over 24 hours [11]. Findings are outlined in Table No.. 6.

10. **Accelerated Stability Testing:** Cream samples were divided into four sections and subjected to stability tests at various temperatures (8°C, 25°C, 40°C to 75% RH) over 8 weeks, with parameters recorded weekly [12]. Results are presented in Table No.. 7.

11. **Spreadability Assessment:** Spreadability was measured by placing a sample between two slides, applying a fixed weight for a set duration to compress them to a uniform thickness, and recording the time required to separate the slides [13]. Spreadability was calculated using a specific formula, and the findings are listed in Table No.. 8.

Formula- $S = M \times L \div T$

where,

S= Spreadability

M= Weight tide of the upper slide, **L=** Length of glass slide

T= Time taken to separate the slides.

12. **Viscosity:** The viscosity of the formulation was assessed utilizing a Brookfield viscometer. Specifically, a Brookfield DV-II + viscometer with an LV-4 spindle was employed for viscosity testing. The prepared formulation was poured into the viscometer's adapter and the rotational speed was incrementally increased from 0.5 to 20 revolutions per minute (r/min) [14]. The findings from this assessment are presented in Table No.. 9.

13. **Phase separation:** The cream that was formulated was stored in a tightly sealed container at room temperature, away from sunlight, and monitored for 24 hours to detect any separation of phases [15-18].

RESULTS

1. **Organoleptic properties:** The organoleptic properties of all six formulations were found to be in Table No.2

Table No. 2. Organoleptic properties

S No..	Formula	Color	Texture	Odour	State
1.	F1	White	Smooth	Characteristics	Semi-solid
2.	F2	White	Smooth	Characteristics	Semi-solid
3.	F3	White	Smooth	Characteristics	Semi-solid
4.	F4	White	Smooth	Characteristics	Semi-solid
5.	F5	White	Smooth	Characteristics	Semi-solid
6.	F6	White	Smooth	Characteristics	Semi-solid

2. **Determination of Type of Emulsion (Dye Method):** The type of emulsion of different

formulations were found to be in Table No..3. Emulsion types

S.no.	Formula	Type of emulsion
1.	F1	Oil in water
2.	F2	Oil in water
3.	F3	Oil in water
4.	F4	Oil in water
5.	F5	Oil in water
6.	F6	Oil in water

3. The pH of the cream: The pH of all formulations is listed in Table No..4

Table No..4. pH of all formulations

S.no.	Formulation	pH
1.	F1	6.31
2.	F2	6.22
3.	F3	6.43
4.	F4	6.66
5.	F5	6.57
6.	F6	6.70

4. Homogeneity: Visual examination and tactile assessment confirm that all formulations achieve a consistent distribution of extracts within the cream.

Table No.. 5 Washability, type of smear after feel test

S.no.	Formulation	Wash ability	Type of smear	After feel	Homogeneity
1.	F1	Easily washable	Nongreasy	Emollient	Good
2.	F2	Easily washable	Nongreasy	Emollient	Good
3.	F3	Easily washable	Nongreasy	Emollient	Good
4.	F4	Easily washable	Nongreasy	Emollient	Good
5.	F5	Easily washable	Nongreasy	Emollient	Good
6.	F6	Easily washable	Nongreasy	Emollient	Good

9. Irritancy test: During irritancy studies, none of the formulations exhibited redness, swelling, inflammation, or irritation. These formulations are

considered safe for use on the skin. Details can be found in Table No. 6.

Table No. .6. Irritancy test

S.no.	Formulation	Irritant effect	Erythema	Edema
1	F1	Nil	Nil	Nil
2	F2	Nil	Nil	Nil
3	F3	Nil	Nil	Nil
4	F4	Nil	Nil	Nil
5	F5	Nil	Nil	Nil
6	F6	Nil	Nil	Nil

10. Stability Testing: After 8 weeks, F1, F2 and F6 show No. change in colour while F3, F4, and F5 show change in colour to yellowish white as shown in Fig No. 9, 10. The results are listed in Table No. 7.

Table No. 7. Stability studies after 20 days

Formula	Formulation	pH after 20 days	Colour after 20 days	Phase separation	Texture	State	Odor
1.	F1	6.47	White	No phase separation	Smooth	Semi-solid	Characteristics
2.	F2	6.29	White	No phase separation	Smooth	Semi-solid	Characteristics
3.	F3	6.58	Yellowish white	No phase separation	Smooth	Semi-solid	Characteristics
4.	F4	6.69	Yellowish white	No phase separation	Smooth	Semi-solid	Characteristics
5.	F5	6.54	Yellowish white	No phase separation	Smooth	Semi-solid	Characteristics
6.	F6	6.99	White	No phase separation	Smooth	Semi-solid	Characteristics

Fig No. 9. Stability studies after 20 days F3, F4, and F5 after 8 weeks

Fig No. 10. Stability studies after 20 days F1, F2 and F6 after 8 weeks.

11. Spreadability: The Spreadability of all formulations is listed in Table No. .8.

Table No. 8. Spreadability studies

S.no.	Formulation	Time in seconds	Spreadability in gm cm/sec	Viscosity (cps)
1.	F1	300	7.5	48690
2.	F2	300	7.6	48880
3.	F3	300	7.8	48780
4.	F4	300	8.0	48888
5.	F5	300	8.1	48891
6.	F6	300	8.1	48889

DISCUSSION

The research was primarily aimed at formulating and evaluating an anti-aging cream utilizing extracts from okra or rice to combat skin aging. The overarching goal was to develop a cream that is both stable and efficacious, with a focus on assessing its performance as a skincare product. The pH levels of the creams ranged from 6.3 to 6.9, which aligns well with the natural pH of the skin, indicating their suitability for use. Notably, all formulations exhibited pH levels closely resembling those of the skin: F1-6.31, F2-6.22, F3-6.43, F4-6.66, F5-6.57, and F6-6.70. Through dye testing, it was confirmed that all formulations adopted an oil-in-water emulsion type, with formulations F1, F2, and F6 demonstrating superior stability in this regard. Visual and tactile assessments revealed a uniform distribution of extracts and consistent coloration across all formulations. Furthermore, formulations F1, F3, and F6 exhibited No. alteration in color over time, indicating their longevity and stability. The creams were found to be easily spreadable, with formulations F2, F4, and F6 displaying enhanced spreadability characteristics. Upon application, the creams left a non-greasy residue on the skin and could be effortlessly removed with tap water, highlighting their user-friendliness. Importantly, none of the formulations elicited any adverse

reactions such as redness or irritation during irritancy studies, underscoring the safety for skin application. Accelerated stability testing conducted at elevated temperatures for 20 days yielded satisfactory outcomes for all formulations, further validating their potential for long-term efficacy and stability.

Future Prospective

Okra stands out as a remarkable vegetable, meeting the criteria of a "super vegetable" due to its numerous benefits and widespread recognition. Its potential as a comprehensive anti-aging agent, without any adverse effects, underscores its significance. Furthermore, scientific investigations highlight the promising prospect of okra as a competitive source of medicinal material, particularly as a nutraceutical. Research focuses on exploring the polysaccharides present in okra mucilage, aiming to amplify their volume and isolate essential medicinal compounds. These nutraceuticals serve dual purposes as medications and dietary supplements, suggesting a multifaceted utility of okra in healthcare. Additionally, okra holds biological importance as an anti-aging agent, antioxidant, anticancer treatment, and anti-inflammatory medication. Scientific evidence also suggests its immunomodulatory effects in bacterial infections.

The potential of okra extracts as a natural and potent ingredient in anti-aging skincare products, when applied topically, is gaining attention. Its bioactive compounds, comprising vitamins, minerals, antioxidants, and polysaccharides, demonstrate remarkable antiaging properties, contributing to improved skin hydration, reduction in wrinkle formation, and enhanced skin elasticity. Moreover, by inhibiting enzymes associated with skin aging and scavenging free radicals, okra extracts shield the skin from oxidative stress and inflammation. Despite these promising findings, further research is warranted to determine the optimal formulations and concentrations for topical application, as well as to elucidate the underlying mechanisms of action of okra extracts in combating skin aging. Nevertheless, the potential benefits of okra for skin health and anti-aging research present an exciting avenue for exploration and hold promising prospects in the cosmetics industry.

CONCLUSION

The findings from these studies indicate that the formulations comprising okra and rice extracts, specifically F1, F2, and F6, along with the base of the anti-aging cream, exhibited higher levels of stability and safety compared to the other formulations. Conversely, the remaining formulations demonstrated instability and exhibited changes in color upon prolonged storage. Notably, these stable formulations maintained consistent pH levels, displayed homogeneity, offered emollient properties left a non-greasy residue post application, and were easily removable. Further scientific investigations will be conducted to comprehensively explore the synergistic effects of the selected formulation components.

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